

THE SUBJECT OF HISTORY TEACHING METHODS AND ITS MAIN TASKS

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Tarix o'qitish metodikasi yo'nalishi talabasi

Annotation: *This article describes in detail the subject of history teaching methods and its main tasks, the purpose of history in general secondary schools and the role of methods in teaching, teaching students through historical material.*

Key words: *methodology, observation method, experimental method, experimental research, historical material.*

Introduction:

An important goal of history in general secondary schools is to acquaint students with the most important events in the history of our country and the world from ancient times to the present day, to acquaint them with the cultural and spiritual heritage of Uzbekistan and its peoples. world. Nurturing in the spirit of respect for national values, national and universal traditions, nurturing worthy heirs who will be the next successors of our great heritage, as well as enriching it.

History teaching methodology is a scientific and pedagogical science based on a history course taught in secondary and special secondary education in order to provide students with in-depth knowledge of history, to educate and bring them up in secondary schools. the spirit of national perspective. clearly defines the purpose, educational work, content, methods, as well as the most important methods of teaching history.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The introduction of the methodology of teaching history as an important subject in the curriculum of historical institutes of higher education and its study will help students to become future teachers in secondary education and secondary special education. introduction to the scientific basis of teaching history in the education system. The methodology of teaching history has its own subject of independent study. The teaching of history and the study of the teaching process in the system of secondary education and secondary special education constitute the subject of the methodology of teaching history. The teaching process has its own laws and regulations that apply objectively.

The process of teaching history can be studied in two ways.

The first is the observation method. When using this method, a variety of educational and methodical literature, written activities of students, reports, their answers, assessments and conclusions on teaching, lessons are observed, students' knowledge and skills are studied in depth. . Also, when using the observation method, the researcher does not deviate from the circle of existing experience of teaching history, observes it naturally and studies it extensively.

The second is the experimental method. The teacher organizes the teaching activity as he wishes. However, the difference between the creative research conducted by the teacher and the scientific experiment is that first the teacher solves a practical task in the classroom, and his conclusions are the result of his own work. The scientific experiment examines the laws that are common to many teachers, and draws conclusions on a scientific basis. Therefore, it is important to distinguish between the method of observation in the study of the process of teaching history and experimental research.

Results:

The history course in secondary and tertiary special education is very rich and varied in content. The meaning of the course of history is that in the system of secondary education and secondary special education, through its educational activities, it affects the minds, education and thinking of students, helping them to develop. will give.

Therefore, the content of the lesson is an important principle for further improving the quality and effectiveness of teaching history in secondary education and secondary special education, the comprehensive improvement of the educational process of schoolchildren. Thus, the teacher must take into account the content of the historical material taught in the independent selection of methodological methods and tools that have a positive impact on the formation of the learning process and ensure the effectiveness of teaching in general.

The methodology of teaching history creates the laws that occur in the strictly repetitive interactions and connections between the components of the process, as well as clearly shows the instructions for their use in the development of the process of teaching history . The teaching methodology uses some research methods of history to help students better master their knowledge and introduce them to some research methods of history.

Discussion:

The methodology of teaching history is inextricably linked with the science of history. Teaching history involves telling students a historical event. In this

sense, students' ways of understanding historical reality are like historical research. In the process of studying history, students use facts that have been scientifically researched and analyzed by scholars, as well as general conclusions to further clarify facts, draw general conclusions from historical facts, and explore new facts. possible. However, students' study of history is completely different from the study of history. During the course, students will be introduced to history and some of its research methods.

The knowledge that students acquire in the process of analyzing new facts and drawing the necessary conclusions from them will be very strong and convincing, and students will also learn to think independently, which will help them become more familiar with the initial methods of research. The methodology uses historical sources, facts, and general conclusions to explain the basics of the science of history.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be noted that the science of history and the methodology of teaching history have their own separate object of study, task and research method. History studies the development of human society. Knowledge of the laws of development of human society allows us to better understand history and the present, to anticipate the future. Methodology Methods of studying the process of teaching history in order to increase the effectiveness of teaching teachers, revealing the components of the process of teaching history in secondary education and secondary special education and the legitimate relationship between them also armed with.

REFERENCES:

1. The single concept of teaching and studying the history of Uzbekistan.- T.: 2014.
2. T.Rahmatullayev. Use of archeological materials in the study of the history of the peoples of Uzbekistan T.Teacher. 2005.
3. Fuzailova GS, Rakhmatullaeva OR "Methods of teaching history in professional fields." Methodical manual. - T., TDPU, 2012.
4. J. Rakhimov Use of archival sources in the study of the history of Uzbekistan. T. Teacher. 2002.
5. Ishmuhamedov R. Ways to increase the effectiveness of education with the help of innovative technologies. - T., TDPU named after Nizami, 2009.